

Spectroscopic and Computational Insights into β -Caryophyllene: α -Cyclodextrin Complex

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Abstract- Molecular docking and phase solubility studies were carried out to explore the inclusion behavior of β -caryophyllene (BCP) within α -cyclodextrin (α -CD) cavities, aiming to improve its aqueous solubility and potential bioavailability. Optimized molecular structures of BCP and α -CD were employed in docking simulations to predict host-guest interactions, binding orientations, and stabilization mechanisms. The docking results indicated that BCP fits partially within the hydrophobic cavity of α -CD, forming a stable complex. Complementary phase solubility analysis was performed by equilibrating BCP with increasing concentrations of α -CD, and the resulting UV-absorbance data were used to construct a phase solubility diagram. A linear profile was obtained, suggesting a 1:1 stoichiometric inclusion complex between BCP and α -CD. The apparent stability constant was calculated from the slope of the solubility curve, indicating a moderate binding affinity that facilitates improved solubility of BCP. Further, BCP and α -CD liquid inclusion is carried out to study their absorption and emission capacity. These findings highlight the potential of α -CD as a suitable carrier for BCP encapsulation, providing a foundation for enhanced formulation strategies.

Keywords – β -caryophyllene, α -cyclodextrin, Host-guest interaction, molecular docking, phase solubility, Liquid Inclusion, Absorption, Emission.

I. INTRODUCTION

β -Caryophyllene (BCP) is a bicyclic sesquiterpene found in essential oils of *Cannabis sativa*, clove, and black pepper, exhibiting a wide range of pharmacological activities, including anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and anticancer effects [1]. However, its practical application is limited due to poor water solubility, low stability, and reduced bioavailability [2]. To address these challenges, inclusion complexation with cyclodextrins (CDs) has emerged as a promising strategy to enhance the solubility and stability of hydrophobic bioactives [3].

Cyclodextrins are cyclic oligosaccharides composed of six (α -CD), seven (β -CD), or eight (γ -CD) glucopyranose units with a hydrophilic exterior and a hydrophobic cavity that allows the encapsulation of guest molecules [4]. Among these, α -CD has been widely studied for forming stable inclusion complexes with small hydrophobic compounds due to its cavity dimensions and favorable binding interactions [5].

Recent research highlights the role of α -CD not only as a carrier but also as a potential bioactivity enhancer due to its ability to form stable, water-soluble complexes that improve the pharmacokinetic behavior of hydrophobic drugs [6]. Advanced silico docking techniques are now used to predict not only binding orientations but also the thermodynamic feasibility of complexation, offering molecular-level insights that guide experimental approaches [7].

In addition, phase solubility studies have evolved as a critical method to quantitatively assess inclusion efficiency and to determine important parameters such as the complexation efficiency (CE) and drug-to-carrier molar ratios [8]. Combining molecular docking with phase solubility profiling creates a robust strategy for screening potential CD carriers before scaling up to formulation studies [9].

The hydrophobic cavity of α -cyclodextrin (α -CD) modifies the electronic environment of the guest molecule, which can be detected through UV-Vis absorption and fluorescence spectroscopy. Bathochromic shifts and intensity changes in these spectra confirm encapsulation and microenvironmental alterations [10-11]

Furthermore, there is growing evidence that CD encapsulation of sesquiterpenes like BCP can significantly enhance their biological performance, including increased antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activity due to improved dispersion and solubility [12]. This dual approach-computational prediction coupled with experimental validation-offers a comprehensive pathway to optimize the encapsulation of BCP with α -CD for pharmaceutical or nutraceutical applications.

Molecular docking serves as a powerful *in silico* tool to predict the orientation, binding energy, and stabilization forces such as hydrophobic and van der Waals interactions between host and guest molecules [13]. Complementary experimental studies, such as phase solubility analysis, are crucial to confirm the stoichiometry and stability constant (K1:1) of the inclusion complex, often identified through linear AL-type diagrams [7].

In this work, the inclusion of BCP within α -CD is investigated through BCP absorption and emission spectra were recorded at various α -CD concentrations to investigate liquid inclusion complex formation, molecular docking and phase solubility studies to understand its binding behavior and evaluate α -CD's potential as a carrier to improve BCP solubility and bioavailability.

II. EXPERIMENTAL APPROACH

2.1 Preparation of liquid inclusion complexes

30 ml of deionized water was used to dissolve 0.0583 g of α -CD and 10ml of ethanol to dissolve 0.0040 g of BCP. The α -CD concentration was varied to create the liquid inclusion complexes. Spectroscopy of liquid inclusion complexes was recorded using UV-Vis & Fluorescence spectroscopy. Scott Christian College's Systronic Double Beam Spectrophotometer-2203 and JASCO Spectrofluorometer FP-8200 are used to record the UV-Vis and fluorescence spectra analysis. Binding constant for both absorption and emission spectra were calculate from Bensi-Hildebrand equation[14].

Figure 1. Workflow of Liquid Inclusion

2.2 Molecular Docking Studies

To elucidate the host-guest interactions between β caryophyllene (BCP) and cyclodextrins (α CD and β CD), a molecular docking analysis was performed using computational tools.

2.2.1 Ligand Preparation (BCP)

The 3D structure of BCP was retrieved from the PubChem database in Structure Data File (SDF) format. The SDF file was converted into Protein Data Bank (PDB) format using AutoDock software to ensure compatibility with docking tools.

2.2.2 Host Preparation (Cyclodextrins)

The structures of α CD was obtained from the Protein Data Bank (PDB) or built. Polar hydrogens and Gasteiger charges were added using AutoDock Tools (ADT).

2.2.3 Docking Setup

The docking process was carried out using AutoDock Vina, which provides an efficient scoring function and search algorithm to determine the best binding orientation. The docking grid box was centered around the cavity of the cyclodextrin molecule, with dimensions large enough to accommodate BCP in multiple orientations.

2.2.4 Docking Simulation

BCP (ligand) was docked into the host molecule (α CD) separately. For each docking run, 10 binding poses were generated and ranked based on binding affinity (kcal/mol). The pose with the lowest binding energy (most negative value) was selected as the optimal inclusion complex.

Figure 2. Workflow of Molecular Docking

2.3 Solubility Enhancement Study

Different concentrations of the host chemical α -CD are used to assess the BCP component's solubility [7]. 30 ml of double-distilled water is used to dissolve 0.291 g of α -CD, and 10ml of ethanol is used to dissolve 0.0204 g of BCP. Various concentrations of α -CD are combined with BCP and shaken continuously for 72 hours. Scott Christian College's Systronic Double Beam Spectrophotometer-2203 at Nagercoil is used to record the UV-Vis spectra analysis.

Figure 3. Phase Solubility Study Process

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Absorption study of liquid inclusion complexes

Figure 4. Absorption of BCP with α -CD at different concentration

Table 1 Absorption of BCP with α -CD at different concentration

Concentration of α -CD	λ_{\max}	Absorbance
0	205	1.417
0.002	206	1.500
0.004	207.8	1.498
0.006	208.2	1.617
0.008	210	1.690
0.01	211.8	2.149

Table 1 and Figure 4 display the various α -CD concentrations utilized in the BCP absorption research. The wavelength shifts and absorbance fluctuations show changes in the electronic environment, indicating the interaction between BCP and α -CD. The absorbance gradually increases from 1.497 to 2.149, as shown in the peak first seen at a higher wavelength. For the BCP, the λ_{\max} value is 205 nm, and it rises to 211.8 nm as the concentration rises. A robust host-guest interaction is suggested by this upward shift in wavelength and absorbance intensity, which validates that BCP and α -CD successfully formed an inclusion complex.

3.2 Fluorescence study of liquid inclusion complexes

The fluorescence analysis of BCP at different doses of α -CD is shown in Figure 5 and Table 2. The emission wavelength shows a steady bathochromic change (red shift) when the α -CD concentration rises, gradually shifting from 300.8 nm to 320 nm. This change toward longer wavelengths points to important interactions between the α -CD cavity and BCP. Further evidence for the creation of an inclusion complex comes from the simultaneous increase in wavelength and fluorescence intensity with increasing α -CD concentrations.

Figure 5. Fluorescence Emission of BCP with α -CD at different concentration

Table 2. Fluorescence Emission of BCP with α -CD at different concentration

Concentration of α -CD	λ_{\max}	Intensity
0	300.8	260
0.002	303.2	263
0.004	308	265
0.006	312.8	268.2
0.008	317.6	272
0.01	320	275.6

3.3 Molecular Docking

The 3D molecular docking visualization of BCP inside the α -CD cavity is shown in Figure 6(c), while Table 3 summarizes the docking results, including binding affinity and RMSD values. Among the docking models, Mode 1 exhibits the lowest binding affinity of -3.965 kcal/mol and an RMSD of zero, indicating that this is the most favorable and stable orientation of BCP within the α -CD cavity. The close binding affinities of Modes 2 to 4 (ranging from -3.91 to -3.82 kcal/mol) suggest alternative docking orientations that are slightly less stable but still feasible. RMSD values below 2 Å for most modes reflect consistent and reliable binding poses predicted by AutoDock Vina.

The negative binding energy highlights a thermodynamically favorable inclusion process, mainly stabilized by hydrophobic interactions between the nonpolar BCP molecule and the hydrophobic inner cavity of α -CD. Such affinity values are comparable to those reported for other terpene-cyclodextrin complexes, confirming the suitability of α -CD for encapsulating BCP.

Figure 6. 3D structure of (a) BCP, (b) α -CD, (c) BCP docked with α -CD

Table 3. auto dock vina results of BCP with α -CD

Mode	Affinity (kcal/mol)	Dist from Rmsd L.B	Dist from Rmsd U.B
1	-3.965	0	0
2	-3.91	1.351	3.641
3	-3.83	1.82	3.201
4	-3.819	1.324	4.366
5	-3.727	1.258	2.949
6	-3.695	1.262	3.629
7	-3.435	1.823	4.01
8	-3.433	1.628	3.192
9	-3.129	1.28	4.163

3.4 Solubility Enhancement Study

Figure 7 illustrates the phase solubility profile of BCP in the presence of increasing α -CD concentrations. The linear increase in BCP concentration with rising α -CD levels indicates the formation of a 1:1 host–guest inclusion complex, as described by the Higuchi–Connors model. The straight line in the plot indicates A_L -type phase solubility behavior because it shows that the host forms a soluble complex alongside the controlled release of the guest molecule at higher concentrations. The stability constant ($K_{1:1}$) of the BCP: α -CD inclusion complex was determined to be 51 M^{-1} , indicating moderate binding strength between the host and guest molecules.

Figure 7. Phase Solubility for BCP: α -CD

IV. CONCLUSION

Molecular docking, phase solubility, and absorption–emission studies collectively confirm the successful formation of a stable BCP: α -CD inclusion complex. Docking revealed a favorable binding orientation with a binding energy of -3.965 kcal/mol , while the A_L -type phase solubility curve ($K_{1:1}=51\text{M}^{-1}$) confirmed a 1:1 stoichiometry and significant solubility enhancement. The bathochromic shifts in both absorption (205 to 211.8 nm) and fluorescence emission (300.8 to 320 nm), along with increased intensity, further validate the strong host–guest interactions and micro-environmental changes upon encapsulation.

Future work could focus on molecular dynamics simulations to explore the stability of the inclusion complex in solution, thermodynamic studies to evaluate enthalpy–entropy contributions, and biological assessments to determine improvements in bioavailability and therapeutic efficacy. Investigating other cyclodextrin derivatives could further optimize BCP delivery.

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